

Phytochemical Diversity in Ayurvedic Formulations: Insights from Modern Analytical Techniques

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Abstract

Ayurvedic formulations constitute a group of phytochemicals and include alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, glycosides and terpenoids, tannins which aid in the potentiation of therapeutic activity. These bioactive components have anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory and neuroprotective effects. The composition of probiotics, however, also shows high variation due to genetic, environmental and processing conditions, which creates a challenge in maintaining a similar treatment effect. Industrial preparations may degrade the quality of phytochemicals as compared to Ayurvedic preparations which focus on holistic extraction. The diversity of the phytochemicals identified in Ayurvedic formulations is explored in this review, mainly concentrating on their pharmacological properties and the potential challenges raised due to their variability. The effects of geographical conditions, seasonal variations and post-harvest processing on the stability of the phytochemicals have been discussed along with improvement in standardization methods. Contemporary analytical strategies like Chromatography, Spectroscopy and bioassays function as essential tools to profile and validate the phytochemicals, facilitating their therapeutic reproducibility. Future studies must be centered around integrating AI-driven phytochemical databases, evolving extraction techniques and setting up global regulatory frameworks. Ayurveda may bolster its position as an evidence-based medical system whilst preserving the purity and efficiency of phytochemically-rich formulations by integrating traditional wisdom along with scientific advances.

Keywords: Phytochemical Diversity, Ayurvedic Formulations, Polyherbal Synergy, Bioactive Compounds, Analytical Techniques, Standardization Challenges, Chromatography, Spectroscopy

Introduction

Ayurveda is an ancient and traditional medical system. It is focused on the medicinal and therapeutic use of plant-based formulations with phytochemical diversity. Ayurvedic plants possess many bioactive molecules, for example, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, terpenoids, glycosides and tannins, however, each bioactive class has different pharmacological activities [1]. Ayurvedic formulations are single compound ayurvedic formulations which show the bioavailability of phytoconstituents by the advantages of synergistic interactions but rather than the safety and therapeutic properties of synthetic drugs which establish composition [2]. They have a

wide spectrum of various pharmacological, anti-microbial, neuroprotective, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and anti-oxidative activities [3, 4]. Although regardless of having potential, reproducibility, quality control and standardization of the phytochemicals stays as significant challenge [5].

Due to various factors like genetic influences, soil composition and seasonal variations, the phytochemical composition of the medicinal plants is inherently variable [6]. For an instance the concertation of the alkaloids and flavonoids alters drastically by pH and climate change in a specific plant species [7]. Additionally, the bioavailability and stability of the compounds can also be affected by conditions like harvesting time, extraction method and storage conditions. [8]. Modern large-scale processing frequently usually departs from the thorough guidelines regarding plant collection and preparation as mentioned in Ayurvedic texts, leading to inconsistent phytochemical profiling [9]. Thus, sustaining the integrity and uniformity of bioactive compounds throughout the batches of Ayurvedic formulations, continues to be the crucial research focus [10].

Advancements in chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques have aided in the more accurate understanding of the phytochemical diversity and standardization in Ayurvedic medicines [11]. Identification and quantification of such bioactive compounds were also based on highly precise and instrumental techniques i.e., High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) and Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) [12]. However, the structural information of the complex phytochemical in can be achieved by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectra and Fourier Transformation Infrared Spectroscopy. (FTIR) [13].

Bioassays like anti-oxidants and anti-inflammatory assays aids in validating the functional efficiency of these compounds including their chemical characterization [14]. A comprehensive and standardized approach to assess the phytochemicals in Ayurveda is unavailable, which limits its acceptance int international health care systems [15].

Prospective investigations ought to concentrate to develop an standardized phytochemical databases refinement of extraction techniques and integration of AI-driven analytical tools for quality control as a means to officially identify Ayurveda as an evidence-based system [6]. Regulatory frameworks must prioritise the integration of Ayurvedic principles along with current scientific validation for reproducibility and global acceptance [10]. The variety of phytochemicals present in the Ayurvedic formulations, their pharmacological magnitude, factors affecting their composition and challenges in their standardization are being explored in this review. Modern analytical techniques for phytochemical profiling are also explored to emphasize the need of integration of traditional Ayurvedic knowledge along with modern scientific advances [11].

2. Phytochemical Diversity in Ayurvedic Formulations

Specific pharmacological properties of variety of phytochemicals are the basis to achieve the multiple therapeutic potential of Ayurvedic formulations. Various health potentials: Numerous health related properties like antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, neuroprotective, and immunomodulatory activities have been confirmed of such bioactive agents including alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, terpenes, glycosides as well as tannins [1].

Unlike pharmaceutical drugs which are single molecule entities, ayurvedic formulations on the other hand are based on a scheme of phytochemical synergy involving multiple phytochemicals in rendering their efficacy,

bioavailability and toxicity [2].The classification, interaction and the factors affecting the variation in phytochemicals are being explored in this section:

2.1 Classification of Phytochemicals in Ayurveda

Alkaloids: These are nitrogen-containing compounds which exhibit analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects. Remarkable examples are piperine of black pepper that aids in absorption of nutrients and Daruharidra in berberine with anti-microbial and anti-diabetic properties [5].

Flavonoids: These are the polyphenolic substances which are known for their anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Some noteworthy examples includes Amla containing quercetin that stabilizes immune function and catechins, present in green tea protect against oxidative stress [7].

Phenolics: These are the free radical scavengers that can provide neuroprotective and anti-aging effects. Turmeric contains curcuminoids, having a strong anti-inflammatory action, and Triphala contains ellagic acid, a good hepatoprotective agent [12].

Terpenoids: These are the bioactive compounds having anti-microbial, adaptogenic, and anti-cancer effects. Notable examples includes Withanolides in the Ashwagandha that helps to promote adaption to stress, Boswellic acids in the Shallaki that offer the anti-arthritis effects [16].

Glycosides: These are the sugar-linked compounds that support cardiovascular and metabolic health functions. These saponins present in Shatavari aids in hormonal balance, and steroidal glycosides in Guduchi that regulate immune function [8].

Tannins: These polyphenols have astringent, antimicrobial, and gut-protective. Remarkable example includes the tannins in Arjuna bark stimulates cardiac function and Haritaki present in Triphala are digestive stimulants [10].

2.2 Synergistic and Antagonistic Interactions in Polyherbal Formulations

Fig. 1. Factors Influencing Phytochemical Profile

The polyherbal nature of the Ayurvedic formulations, that amalgamates multiple phytochemicals in one formulation gives them their therapeutic strength. Synergy occurs when combined effect of phytochemicals outweigh their separate effect enhancing each other’s absorption, bioavailability and pharmacological effects.

Piperine present in Black pepper boosts the anti-inflammatory action of curcuminoids by enhancing its bioavailability [17]. Likewise, flavonoids and tannins present in Triphala collaboratively offers gut-protective and anti-oxidant functions [9]. Although not every interaction is beneficial. A certain number of phytochemicals may possess antagonistic effect, whereby the effectiveness of one compound gets compromised by others. For example, Alkaloids and flavonoids absorption is diminished by high concentrations of Tannins [3]. Optimization of formulation efficiency and ensuring balanced phytochemical composition in Ayurvedic composition necessitates the deeper comprehension of these interaction.

2.3 Factors Influencing Phytochemical Composition

The chemical composition of the medicinal plants is highly variable, due to the many factors influencing their phytochemical profile. Genetic Variation Genetic Variation is the one of most important natural factors influencing phytochemical composition. Different chemotypes of the same plant species may yield different amounts of bioactive compounds. For instance, the Withanolide content of the Ashwagandha plants differ between plants grown in different regions [6].

Fig. 2. Factors Influencing Phytochemical Profile

The synthesis of secondary metabolites is controlled by a number of factors including geographical locations and the climate, such as soil type, altitude and humidity. The content of curcuminoids within turmeric is largely influenced by climate and soil types [10]. Phytochemical concentrations are also influenced by seasonal variability and the and the plant harvesting period. According to the seasonal studies, Tulsi leaves that are harvested earlier contains more essential oils, whilst those harvested afterward contain greater flavonoid content [7].

2.4 Comparing Traditional and Modern Ayurvedic Formulations

Conventional preparative methods are used in traditional Ayurvedic formulations. These methods includes decoction (Kwatha), fermentation (Arishta), and powdered mixtures (Churna) [18]. These methods seeks to maximize the therapeutic potential while preserving the phytochemical integrity [2]. Modern Ayurvedic medications, in contrast, utilizes standardized extract ensuring consistency from batch to batch [15]. Although,

standardization enhances the quality control but it might irradicate the essential phytochemical interaction exhibited by traditional formulations [14].

The depletion of the volatile bioactive compounds due to high temperature extraction techniques is a significant hinderance in modern processing. For example, the heat-sensitive flavonoids and essential oils are sometimes deteriorated by conventional solvent extraction in industrial [1]. The new technologies like Cold percolation techniques and superficial fluid extraction (SFE) are being investigated in order to preserve entire phytochemical integrity and spectrum [13].

2.5 The Need for a Phytochemically Balanced Approach

Maintaining phytochemical integrity is important to assure formulation efficiency and reproducibility in context of increasing global interest in Ayurveda. Although balancing between sustaining the conventional wisdom and integrating contemporary scientific validation proves to be challenging [10]. The synergistic interactions that are the foundation of the Ayurvedic medicine must not be compromised in pretence of standardization regardless how it can increase the credibility [17]. The development of phytochemical fingerprinting databases, processing method optimization and the incorporation of AI-driven analytical tools for quality control are the main focus of contemporary research [6]. Going forward, preserving the full therapeutic potential of Ayurvedic formulations whilst adherence to the global health standards calls for a coordinated approach that will combine phytochemical preservation, standardization and current analytical validation [10].

3. Role of Phytochemicals in Ayurvedic Therapeutics

The pharmacological activity of ayurvedic formulation stem from the large number of phytochemical and compounds induce pathways in the body to prevent diseases and provides health benefits. These bioactive compounds also have anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, neuroprotective, anti-oxidant, anti-microbial, and metabolic controlling actions. These compounds are alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, terpenoids, glycosides and tannin [1]. Ayurveda avails the synergistic phytochemical interactions to enhance bioavailability, prolong therapeutic effect and reduce toxicity as against allopathic medicine which manipulate single target pathways [2]. This section explores the therapeutic functions of Ayurvedic medicines, which are proven by well documented formulations.

3.1 Adaptogenic and Immunomodulatory Effects

Adaptogens are the substances that enhance the body's capacity to maintain homeostasis and recover from stress. A few of the Ayurvedic herbs possessed the immunomodulatory and stress attenuating effects by their various phytochemical active constituents. Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) are loaded with withanolides to improve immune health, balance hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis & resilience to emotional and physical stress [8]. Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*) contain polysaccharides that enhances production of cytokines, activates natural killer (NK) cells and macrophages which enhances the immunity. Triterpenes in Shatavari (*Asparagus racemosus*) regulates oestrogenic activity, it can balance hormones and promote reproductive health [10].

3.2 Anti-Inflammatory and Antioxidant Properties

Chronic diseases, such as arthritis, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases, arise primarily due to inflammation and oxidative stress. Several phytochemicals in the Ayurvedic plants also block pro-inflammatory pathways, scavenge free radicals, and alter cytokine expression. Curcuminoids, a phenolic compound of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), blocks the NF- κ B signalling and inhibits the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 which play a major role in inflammatory diseases [7]. Shallaki (*Boswellia serrata*) contains boswellic acids that block the action of 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX), an enzyme involved in the synthesis of leukotrienes, resulting in less inflammation, and could be useful in asthma and osteoarthritis [12]. Ellagic acid in triphala stimulates anti-oxidant defence mechanism through the Nrf2 mediated expression of anti-oxidant response element [17].

3.3 Neuroprotective and Cognitive-Enhancing Effects

Ancient Ayurvedic herbs have been used for memory improvement, brain function enhancement over the years to prevent Nerve diseases such as Parkinson's disease & Alzheimers. Neurotransmitter modulation, oxidative stress reduction, and neurogenesis induction are their neuroprotective effects. Bacosides, found in Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*) that prevents cognitive decline from having increasing synaptic plasticity, improvement acetylcholine levels, and inhibition of β -amyloid deposition [3]. The ginsenosides contained in Ashwagandha and Shankhpushpi (*Convolvulus pluricaulis*) are responsible for upregulating the expression of the nerve growth factor (NGF) which promotes neuronal regeneration [6]. Conversely, Green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) contains catechin that decrease oxidative stress and improves dopamine regulation by inhibiting monoamine oxidase (MAO) in the pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease [10].

3.4 Antimicrobial and Antiviral Activities

Phytochemicals having anti-bacterial, anti-viral, and anti-fungal have been credited in making very effective Ayurvedic formulations, acting via different mechanisms like by interfering in cell walls & membranes, taming the growth, acting in enzymes, and affecting immune system. Allicin from Garlic (*Allium sativum*) shreds the bacterial cell membranes and arrests even anti-biotic resistant strains of *Escherichia coli* & *Staphylococcus aureus* [2]. As a Potential treatment for Influenza and Herpes Simplex Virus, Tannins are found in Arjuna (*Terminalia arjuna*) that may bind to proteins of the virus to inhibit the growth of the virus [7]. The andrographolides present in Kalmegh, (*Andrographis paniculata*), are known to regulate levels of the immune mediators by inducing interferons, which help fight respiratory infections [1].

3.5 Metabolic and Cardiovascular Benefits

Phytochemicals help lower cholesterol, boost insulin response, and regulates our metabolic pathways which, in many cases, protect against the heart issues. For example, fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*); it has saponins that typically nudge insulin secretion, helping with diabetes management while also limiting glucose absorption in intestines [15]. Amla (*Phyllanthus emblica*) possess flavonoids which are beneficial for preventing oxidative stress of blood vessels, increasing the levels of HDL cholesterol in blood and reducing LDL cholesterol and reduces the risk of atherosclerosis [14]. Berberine in Daruharidra (*Berberis aristata*) elevates lipid metabolism through activation of AMPK & reduces the hazards associated with obesity [5].

3.6 Ayurvedic Formulations with Diverse Phytochemical Profiles

Phytochemical rich Ayurvedic formulations may be more efficient, as they act in multiple bio-pathways at the same time. Chyawanprash is a classical polyherbal formulation comprised of Amla, Ashwagandha & Guduchi which have Immunostimulatory & rejuvenating activity because of the presence of phenols, flavonoids, tannins & saponins [8]. Triphala is a mix of three fruits (Phyllanthus embelica, Terminalia bellirica & Terminalia chebula) for systemic detoxification and Gastrointestinal support, flavonoids, phenolics and tannins [19]. Withanolides, alkaloids, & glycosides in Ashwagandharishta, a fermented Ayurvedic herbal network, increase endurance, reduce stress & manage hormonal equilibrium [9].

4. Challenges in Maintaining Phytochemical Integrity

Phytochemical quality of medicinal plants is indirectly linked with therapeutic efficacy of Ayurvedic preparations. Although, natural variability, adverse environmental effects, processing methods and regulatory gaps raises challenges to maintaining consistency in phytochemical composition. Ayurvedic compounds have a intricate mixture of bioactive compounds that depends on varying factors, contrary to synthetic drugs having precisely established molecular structures [1]. The major factors that influence phytochemical integrity in Ayurvedic formulations are discussed in this section in conjugation their repercussions for therapeutic efficiency and standardization.

4.1 Variability in Phytochemical Yield Across Different Batches

Batch-to-batch variations in phytochemical composition in Ayurvedic formulations is one of the major problems. Chemical variability produced by indigenous medicinal plants are the result of genetic variation, environment and cultural practices [6]. Withanolide content in Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) plants is also known to differ extensively depending on the plant genotype [7]. The production of secondary metabolites is regulated by various geographic and climatic factors such as temperature, precipitation, altitude, soil nutrients and humidity. The content of curcuminoids in turmeric is strongly influenced by climate and the soil type in which it grew [10]. Phytochemical concentrations are also influenced by seasonal variability and the and the plant harvesting period. According to the seasonal studies, Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) leaves that are harvested early morning have high flavonoid content, however it decreases substantially with extended sunlight exposure [7]. These variations hinders in standardization of Ayurvedic formulations, which require accuracy in phytochemical profiling, ensuring therapeutic consistency.

4.2 Impact of Cultivation, Harvesting, and Processing on Phytochemical Stability

The stability and bioavailability of phytochemicals are significantly affected by the processing techniques. Specific harvesting periods and preparation processes can be found in ancient Ayurvedic texts to preserve these bioactive compounds [2]. Although these traditional processes are often modified due to industrial scale production which results into loss of phytochemical integrity. Post-harvesting, the phytochemicals undergoes degradation by improper drying, extended storage and prolonged exposure to heat and moisture. Vitamin C in Amla (*Phyllanthus emblica*) is lost when it is sun-dried, but retains when shed-dried. Catechin, from green tea and some essential oils in peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) are the heat sensitive phytochemicals which can be degraded by high temperature extraction techniques like conventional solvent extraction [12]. The fermentation and storage also plays crucial role to regulate phytochemical stability as some fermented Ayurvedic formulations or Arishtas needs specific microbial conditions in order to develop their phytochemical profile. These

phytochemical transformations can be altered by modern preservation techniques like Artificial stabilizers [17]. To ensure the phytochemical stability we are in need of optimized drying, extraction and storage techniques that goes hand in hand with traditional Ayurvedic practices while utilizing modern preservation techniques.

4.3 Challenges in Standardization of Polyherbal Formulations

Ayurvedic medicines is heavily based on polyherbal formulations leveraging multiple phytochemicals that works in synergy to create therapeutic effects. Standardization of multi-component formulation faces substantial analytical challenges [9]. In contrary to pharmaceuticals having single-compound, these polyherbal formulations have multitude of bioactive compounds that interact dynamically; thus, it is difficult to establish a general yet precise dose-response relationship due to their complex phytochemical interactions [3]. Varying solubility of different phytochemicals which leads to inconsistent extraction efficiency thus necessitating the need of optimized extraction techniques. For example, ethanol is the most effective method for extracting the lipophilic compounds in ashwagandha, whereas aqueous extraction is necessary for the tannins in triphala [5]. Lacking universal standardization protocol is also a major challenge as the quantification of marker compounds is the fundamental of current herbal standardization techniques, which is frequently is not able to capture the entirety of phytochemical profile. Considering turmeric, whose standardization is solely dependent on curcumin content, here other bioactive terpenoids are overlooked that enhances its effectiveness. The proficient analytical techniques like metabolomic fingerprinting, GC-MS, and HPLC are being utilized for improvement of the polyherbal standardization, yet complexity of formulations continues to be a significant challenge.

4.4 Regulatory Gaps in Ayurvedic Herbal Drug Quality Control

Ayurvedic formulations are subjected to regulatory inconsistencies across different regions, contrary to the pharmaceutical medications, which adheres to strict Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) [10]. It is challenging to accept the product efficiency and safety, where Global standards to validate phytochemical and their quality control lacks. The major challenge of this regulatory gap as Divergence in herbal drug regulations as different countries govern different herbal medicine regulatory frameworks [11]. The European Medicines Agency (EMA) has more strict phytochemical validation requirements than FDA from United States, which classifies Ayurvedic herbs only as dietary supplements [15]. Another reason is adulteration and contamination risk. Many commercial Ayurvedic products have been identified to have microbial contamination, which makes herbal adulteration a serious issue [14]. In some cases, therapeutic results can be affected when less expensive drugs are employed instead of genuine medicinal plants [13]. Absence of Complete Phytochemical Databases can be also a major reason as most Ayurvedic phytochemicals do not have standardized chemical databases for references, thus making quality control a challenge, contrary to pharmaceutical medications, having well documented molecular structures [17].

Coordinated international guidelines to validate Ayurvedic phytochemicals which will encompass the advanced analytical techniques along with AI driven quality control system are needed to address these regulatory challenges.

5. Modern Analytical Techniques and Future Directions in Phytochemical Research

Advanced analytical techniques that are able to identify, quantify and validate the bioactive compounds are in need to ensure the phytochemical integrity of Ayurvedic formulations. Modern analytical techniques which includes chromatography, spectroscopy, and bioassay-based validation, provides better precision, reproducibility and phytochemical standardization than the conventional quality assessment which solely relied on sensory evaluation and crude extraction techniques [17]. Future advances are in need for phytochemical validation and regulation, due to lack of Universal standardization, Ayurveda continues to encounter challenge in gaining global acceptance despite of these developments [10].

Separation and quantification of the Phytochemicals must be done using chromatographic techniques like High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), , Thin-Layer Chromatography (TLC) and Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). To ensure batch-to-batch consistency while withanolides quantification in ashwagandha and curcuminoid profiling in turmeric HPLC is frequently used [12]. For rapid identification of marker compounds in Dashmoolarishta, Triphala and Chyawanprash chemical fingerprints are generated by TLC and High-Performance TLC (HPTLC). Bioactive compounds like terpenes and sesquiterpenoids in ayurvedic formulations are volatile in nature and contains of a lot of essential oils. GC-MS can be useful in detecting them [14]. Although Chromatography helps in standardization of processes, yet the complex phytochemical interactions aren't fully taken into account, which are the crucial feature of polyherbal Ayurvedic compositions [3].

The more comprehensive insights into the molecular structure and functional groups of these phytochemical can gained by employing the advanced spectroscopic techniques like UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-Vis), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR) and Fourier Transformation Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). FTIR has been popular for detecting flavonoids, alkaloids and glycosides whereas UV-Vis has been widely used for the determination of phenolics & antioxidants in herbal extracts [13]. NMR spectroscopy is more complicated, but gives much higher resolution structures of phytochemicals and is therefore applied for discovery of novel bioactive principles in Ayurveda [16]. Even though these methods have added advantages, they are mainly focused on individual compounds than on the overall phytochemical profile, thereby restricting the use of these methods for polyherbal standardization [6].

In addition to the above chemical identification, bioassays impose the biological activity of the phytochemicals. Free radical scavenging ability of DPPH and FRAP antioxidant activity assays validate the antioxidant activity of Ayurvedic herbs [5]. Anti-inflammatory and cytotoxicity tests are important to the therapeutic use of the extracts of Shallaki and Guduchi in arthritis and cancer, respectively [2]. In vitro and in vivo studies lend credibility to the reality of neuroprotective, cardioprotective and hepatoprotective effects and thereby link the traditional phytotherapy with the modern pharmacology [15]. But it is lack of standardized bioassay procedure that makes it difficult to have similar evaluation of Ayurvedic formulation [10].

Notwithstanding the technological revolution, Ayurveda continues to face global challenges of standardization, regulatory credibility, and the bastion of allopathic evidence-based system of medicine. The latter study is one of the earliest implementations of phenolic compound identification and their functional fingerprint using a computational AI-based tool, but the AI-enabled phytochemical analysis remains a subject of future research that should consider the predictability of synergistic behaviour between phytochemicals, optimization of protocols involving extraction, and molecular-level fingerprinting [17]. A worldwide phytochemical database for Ayurvedic

preparations will aid in standardisation and uniformity of formulations [6]. The use of cold percolation, supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) and microwave-assisted extraction will retain the entire phytochemical spectrum, preserving the therapeutic efficacy [8]. In addition, amalgamation of Ayurveda and pharmacogenomics will lead to the birth of personalized herbal medicine wherein formulations could be prepared as per an individual's genetic susceptibility [7].

With scientific developments further perfecting phytochemical profiling and bioassay validation and AI-aided standardization, it could be well possible for AY [Ayurveda] to bask the glory of global acceptance retaining its holistic approach towards therapeutics. Integrating the ancient wisdom of Ayurveda and the modern instrumental technique will guarantee that these historical formulations are applicable in modern healthcare [10].

6. Conclusion

Phytochemical variety is the basis of Ayurvedic medicine, which has a wide range of therapeutic indications. The synergistic interplay of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, terpenoids, glycosides, and tannins contributes the bioavailability, pharmacological action, and safety. Despite these several advantages, preserving phytochemical integrity of Ayurvedic formulations remains difficult because of genetic, environmental, and processing-associated changes. In traditional Ayurvedic methods it is important to note that we need to concentrate on the holistic tenant of harnessing everything possible from the plant. The phytochemical profile changes when industrially scaled, due in part to homogenization, which could negatively impact consistency and therapeutic effect.

The advent of current analytical methodologies such as chromatography (HPLC, GC-MS), spectroscopy (FTIR, NMR, UV-Vis) and bioassays play major role in the advancement of phytochemical profiling and standardization. Such tools help in accurate identification, standardization and validation of bioactive ingredients which brings better quality control to Ayurvedic formulations. Nevertheless, such approaches are insufficient to discover all the complex relationship networks in polyherbal compounds and there is a need to explore metabolomics and AI-driven predictive modelling with more depth.

But for Ayurveda to be integrated into the evidence-based pipeline, we need future research to build: a universal database of phytochemicals, utilize advanced extraction methods and establish an AI-based analytical framework, the authors write. International harmonized guidelines for safety and reproducibility of data will integrate these formulations to global healthcare. Through the integration of ancient wisdom and contemporary science, Ayurveda can mature into an internationally validated therapeutic system while retaining its fundamental principles of holistic therapy.

References:

1. Balkrishna, A., Verma, S., Sharma, P., Tomer, M., Srivastava, J., & Varshney, A. (2021). Comprehensive and rapid quality evaluation method for the Ayurvedic medicine Divya-Swasari-Vati using two analytical techniques: UPLC/QTOF MS and HPLC–DAD. *Pharmaceuticals*, 14(4), 297.

2. Govindarajan, N., Chinnapillai, A., Balasundaram, M., Narasimhaji, C. V., Ganji, K., & Raju, I. (2016). Pharmacognostical and phytochemical evaluation of a polyherbal Ayurvedic formulation Trikatu Churna. *Journal of Ayurveda and Medical Sciences*, 1(1), 34–40.
3. Mukherjee, P. K. (2019). Antiviral evaluation of herbal drugs. In *Quality control and evaluation of herbal drugs* (pp. 599–628).
4. Jethva, D., Agrawal, S., & Pandey, A. (2020). Detection of adulterants in polyherbal nutraceutical “Chyawanprash” by phytochemical analysis & quantitative estimation of phytoconstituents by UV spectrophotometry. *International Journal of AYUSH*, 9(2), 82–95.
5. Patil, P. S., & Shettigar, R. (2010). An advancement of analytical techniques in herbal research. *Journal of Advanced Scientific Research*, 1(1), 8–14.
6. Tiwari, D., Kewlani, P., Gaira, K. S., Bhatt, I. D., Sundriyal, R. C., & Pande, V. (2023). Predicting phytochemical diversity of medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) across eco-climatic zones and elevation in Uttarakhand using generalized additive model. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1).
7. Singh, A., Ota, S., Srikanth, N., Galib, R., Bojja, S., & Dhiman, K. S. (2018). Application of spectroscopic and chromatographic methods for chemical characterization of an Ayurvedic Herbo-Mineral preparation: Maha Yograja Guggulu. *Journal of Evidence-Based Integrative Medicine*, 23, 1–8.
8. Kurian, A., George, S., & Thomas, B. (2021). A review on phytochemical characterization of Kwatha–Ayurvedic polyherbal formulation. *Journal of Natural Remedies*, 21(2), 87.
9. Babu, B. V. (2023). Comparative physicochemical evaluation of Ashwagandharista formulations: Traditional vs. modern methods. *Global Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2(8), 1–7.
10. Sahoo, M., Dash, S., Sahoo, A. C., Sahoo, P. K., Rath, S. S., & Muduli, P. (2023). Modern analytical methods for standardization of classical poly herbal formulations: A review. *Journal of Population Therapeutics and Clinical Pharmacology*, 30(17), 368–380.
11. Kulkarni, K., Jagtap, G., & Magdum, S. (2019). A comprehensive review on herbal drug standardization. *American Journal of PharmTech Research*, 9(3), 98–122.
12. Kamali, M., Khosroyar, S., Kamali, H., Sani, T. A., & Mohammadi, A. (2016). Phytochemical screening and evaluation of antioxidant activities of *Dracocephalum kotschyi* and determination of its luteolin content. *Avicenna Journal of Phytomedicine*, 6(4), 425–433.
13. Sanghai, D., Adhate, P., Patil, S., & Sanghai, N. (2011). Development of analytical techniques for identification of phytochemicals in selected herbal drugs. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 2(8), 2126–2131.
14. Vador, N., Vador, B., & Hole, R. (2012). Simple spectrophotometric methods for standardizing Ayurvedic formulation. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 74(2), 161.
15. Akhtar, S., Sharma, S., Bhuyan, N., Shrestha, B., & Baraily, V. (2023). A systematic review of different analytical methods for major phytoconstituents of turmeric and black pepper. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 14(6), 2619–2634.
16. Abraham, A., Samuel, S., & Mathew, L. (2018). Phytochemical analysis of Pathyashadangam kwath and its standardization by HPLC and HPTLC. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*, 11(2), 153–158.
17. Misro, L., Boini, T., Maurya, R., Radhakrishnan, T., Rohith, K. S., Kumar, V., Sharma, P., Singh, A., Singh, R., Srikanth, N., & Acharya, R. (2024). Analytical method development and validation for simultaneous

estimation of seven markers in polyherbal formulation JKC by using RP-HPLC. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 10(1).